

Why RISC-V Matters

ASSESSING THE ACCEPTANCE
OF OPEN-SOURCE INSTRUCTION
SET ARCHITECTURE IN GLOBAL
SEMICONDUCTOR DESIGNING
ECOSYSTEM

By Science and
Technology Centre

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India looks forward to cultivating all the options for an independent supply chain and manufacturing of open source systems.

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Why RISC-V Matters

Qualcomm Technologies, a member of RISE in a blogpost mentioned how the telecom chipmaking giant is 'unlocking the potential of RISC-V.'

Introduction

Why RISC-V Matters

Reduced Instruction Set Computer - V (RISC-V), pronounced as 'risk-five' is an open-source chip architecture famous for its low power consumption, flexibility, and openness.

The semiconductor chips are considered as the meta-technology on which advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), quantum computing, advanced IoT etc. are developed and deployed. The Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) forms a significant part of semiconductor value chain as they create the platforms on which the silicon designs are deployed. The ISA are protected through patented intellectual property license accorded to the developer of the architecture. Currently, the accessibility to this intellectual property of ISA is heavily securitized both by the makers of this IP as well as the nation from which the makers belong.

Contrary to this growing IP protectionism in ISA domain, Reduced Instruction Set Computer- V (RISC-V), pronounced as 'risk-five' is an open-source chip architecture famous for its low power consumption, flexibility, and openness, three of the most important aspect when it comes to developing cores and chipsets mainly in the FPGA and ASIC market, two of the major verticals that have high powered applications that have ability to compute a wide array of data that can be deployed across domains.

Other than flexibility of RISC-V relative to legacy IP protected ISA such as Softbank owned ARM and Intel's x86, the geopolitical position that RISC-V International Association, the governing body of RISC-V as well as the proprietary ISA providers play a significant role in the semiconductor supply chain resilience debate. While all major ISA providers, be it open-source or licensed, claim to take a politically neutral stance. However, the governance structure of these organizations are better variables to assess the political neutrality of these organizations.

For decades since the end of the Cold War, the supply chain of semiconductor and equipment through which they are manufactured has spread across the world. A single computer chip requires more than 1,000 steps and passes through 70 international borders before it finds its way in a personal computer or a data centre.

Supply Chain Resilience in Semiconductors

For a national economy, resilience in supply chain implies that in case of any disruption; natural or human generated, the availability and accessibility of the specific end-product or service stays perennial or 'anti-fragile.'

The phrase 'supply chain resilience,' while creating a mild impression in the minds of the readers as the diplomats, economists, and politicians, often use it as principal keyword in their speeches and policy documents in foreign trade dialogues, the phrase has a deeper geopolitical interpretation in the context of semiconductor ecosystem.

For a national economy, resilience in supply chain implies that in case of any disruption, natural or human generated, the availability and accessibility of the specific end-product or service stays perennial or 'anti-fragile,' a term coined by Naseem Taleeb, a famous author, statistician, and risk analyst. In the context of semiconductor supply chain, the 'resilience' holds a deeper political context which debatably holds greater weight than the economic context in which the term is usually used.

For decades since the end of the Cold War, the supply chain of semiconductor and equipment through which they are manufactured has spread across the world. A single computer chip requires more than 1,000 steps and passes through 70 international borders before it finds its way in a personal computer or a data centre.

China is currently leading the downstream of the semiconductor supply chain, both in the supply-side and demand-side economics related to global semiconductor ecosystem. In the demand side, cutting-edge semiconductor chips have a cross-domain demand in mainland China, including in the military, which stands as the principal source of concern for the government of the United States and its military establishment.

Disallowing access to such meta-technologies to China has stayed as the top priority of the US foreign policy, as China holding a huge stake in the downstream supply chain of the cutting-edge semiconductor chips is detrimental to America's position in the global military balance of power.

Parallely, in supply-side, Chinese chip makers have achieved a significant amount of dexterity in advanced packaging which forms the basis of the chipsets. Also, in memory chip, Chinese chip makers such as Yangtze Memory Technologies Corporation, an industry leader in NAND chips and Semiconductor Manufacturing International Corporation, a pure-play foundry, debatably holds a critical edge over their western counterparts such as Micron or Samsung. However, the recent regulations by the United States have caused a disruption for the Chinese chipmakers who heavily rely on the western semiconductor equipment manufacturer without whom it is practically impossible to develop advanced chip designs and manufactured into the end-products through chip fabrication (foundry) process.

Hence, achieving resilience implies channelizing the supply-side downstream of the semiconductor value chain to other global economies that holds a relatively better geopolitical consensus with the United States than China does. This re-channelization often is at the cost of disrupting the market share of Chinese tech ecosystem, which is surely in the case in contemporary semiconductor ecosystem. However, the question is what really drives this resilience? Is it government regulations or the national ecosystems that forms the basis of the resilience? The answer is both and none at the same time.

The decisive factor that drives resilience are not only the governments or militaries of these two great nations, but also the private companies who have invested billions in commercializing these technologies for a wider civilian market. These corporates form the nuclei of the global semiconductor ecosystem.

The decision made by the corporate leadership of these companies have as deeper and wider influence on the global politics as the executive orders signed by the President of the United States or China or the bills passed by the United States Congress or State Council of the People's Republic of China.

Majority of the industry leaders are of the opinion that the Moore's Law has come to its limit which demands innovation, not only in how chips are manufactured, but also in how they are designed at an 'angstrom' level. This requires quick commercialization of the technological innovations.

The very founders of the semiconductor industry ensured that they diversify their commercial revenue from government contracts by tapping the civilian market. Bob Noyce, one of the key innovators of integrated circuits in 1965 while working at Fairchild Semiconductors, understood that military and space application of semiconductor chips won't suffice for long-term sustenance of the industry. As a result, he always envisioned a large civilian market that needed to be created for which he required to keep the "Pentagon at arm's length" since government contracts entail secrecy and terms & conditions that strangles innovation which requires openness and collaborations.

Since then, Fairchild Semiconductors ensured that the Defense Department's research and development contribution stays limited to only 4 percent of Fairchild's annual R&D budget. The emerging market of integrated circuits was turning lucrative as new industry players started entering the ecosystem of semiconductor chips and went on to create the modern supply chain throughout the Cold War era.

In a famous case, one of the Fairchild Semiconductors' employees in his exit questionnaire wrote "I...WANT...TO ...GET...RICH," as the reason behind leaving the company as the competition created greater job opportunities for electronic engineers. This event has symbolized the commercial lucrativeness the semiconductor market holds in the civilian applications while at the same time, the concern of its military application has stayed perennial for years now. Military hardware such as cruise missiles, hypersonic missiles, drones, and defense based IoT rely on the FPGA cores and chipsets that are designed on the platforms of these ISA makers.

Such applications require accuracy and precision, which demands heavy computing capabilities, a need fulfilled by the cutting-edge chip designs developed by Fabless chip companies. Artificial Intelligence, often considered as the next military offset after nuclear weapons, relies heavily on the semiconductor products such as Graphical Processing Unit, Neural Processing Unit, Field Programmable Gate Arrays, and others which are the workhorse of computing a huge array of data for specific domain applications. Advanced chips are required to run AI integrated military command and control centers to increase the efficiency of an army's C4ISR capabilities. These products rely on a specific set of instructions that are embedded in the architecture of these chips on which the chips are designed.

Hence, 'supply chain resilience' demands derisking of market positions that the global corporates hold while at the same time ensuring the demand side of the civilian market stays perennial as the industry demands a continuous flow of wealth for developing newer and better products that have cross-domain applications.

In the midst of growing geopolitical turbulence between the United States and People's Republic of China, the significance of RISC-V has increased like never before. Started as a funded project in UC Berkeley, a university in California, RISC-V Foundation was created in 2014 in Delaware, United States as the governing body of the RISC-V ecosystem.

The Curious Case of RISC-V

In the midst of growing geopolitical turbulence between the United States and People's Republic of China, significance of RISC-V has increased like never before.

While proprietary ISA providers reportedly have a lesser malleability in terms of changing the core architecture of the chip, RISC-V claims to provide that flexibility to chipmakers who need to manipulate the very architecture of the chip.

In the midst of growing geopolitical turbulence between the United States and People's Republic of China, significance of RISC-V has increased like never before. What started as a funded project in UC Berkeley, a university in California, RISC-V Foundation was created in 2014 in Delaware, United States as the governing body of the RISC-V ecosystem. However, to protect the ecosystem from the disruptive trade practices of the Trump administration, the organization was later rechristened as RISC-V International Association and the headquarters were shifted from Delaware to Zurich, Switzerland in March 2020 to protect the political neutrality of the organization.

The open-source movement in ISA is more appealing to Chinese chip designers who are affected by the western sanctions over their access to ARM and Intel's x86 proprietary based ISA, an established set of chip architecture that dominates the global computing electronics in retail as well as business space. An open-source architecture allows anyone to access, inspect, modify, and distribute its source code, a set of instructions that tells the software connected to hardware through a compiler and interpreter, how to work. Products such as Bluetooth have an open-access source code for all the developers who use these technologies to create their own products.

In fact, electricity is considered as the first such core technology that was kept open-source through which other innovative products such as bulbs was created.

On the other hand, proprietary architecture is owned and controlled by a single individual or company that has closely guarded the source code of the architecture. Such architecture is accessible only to the selected teams or groups who own the exclusive right to sell or use the architecture. The user of the architecture has to pay a fee or obtain a license from the ISA patent holder and is subject to certain terms and conditions set by the owner of the architecture, in this case, ARM and Intel who have developed their proprietary chip ISA on which almost all the advanced semiconductor chips work.

ARM chips are widely deployed in everyday consumer electronics and smartphones while x86 mainly focuses on the domain of microprocessors used in laptops, personal computers as well as high performance data centers, server farms, and cloud service providers. The ability to modify, and share the source code by open-source ISA as opposed to proprietary ISA allows new chip designing entrants to leapfrog into the chip designing industry.

RISC-V is highly accepted in certain niche sectors where users of the service need over-the-top applications that conventional hardware is not designed to perform. Two chipmakers, Ventana Systems and InCore Semiconductors develop their chips based on RISC-V ecosystem whose cases are explained in detail ahead in the report.

RISC-V Software Ecosystem (RISE), a group of existing cutting-edge chipmakers, includes Qualcomm, Google, Intel, NVIDIA, Samsung, and few others including Ventana is hosted by Linux Foundation that focuses on developing performance based and power-efficient RISC-V cores that runs on high level operating systems for a variety of market segments.

Qualcomm, a master in smartphone chips has announced its plans to create RISC-V compatible products. The recent launch of Snapdragon 865 platform is fully integrated with RISC-V microcontrollers as it provided the ability to control something very specific within a block inside their chip. In a press statement, Qualcomm declares that it has till now shipped more than 650 million RISC-V cores.

Key benefits of RISC-V

1. Flexibility

Chip designers leveraging RISC-V get more freedom to change a specific instruction within the chip architecture based on their need that proprietary ISA cannot provide. The most important thing about RISC-V is that it's free. Meaning anyone with enough VLSI talent and acumen to convert an idea into an economically viable business solution can leverage RISC-V and save tons of business capital investment in licensing fees to proprietary ISA.

2. Scalability

While the aspect of scalability of ISA is subject to acceptance in the industry depending on how much reliable the regulators of RISC-V are, there are some specific cases where RISC-V is leveraged at an unprecedented scale. The Institute of Software at the Chinese Academy of Sciences (ISCAS) has been working on developing 2,000 RV64GC laptops based on the RISC-V ISA as it intends to reduce its reliance on ARM and Intel.

3. Political neutrality

The turbulent political environment and the growing geopolitical rivalry between the United States and China has also affected the supply chain of semiconductor manufacturing since these products travel through multiple international borders, given how globalized the value chain of semiconductor market is. RISC-V which is managed by a board of private companies has shifted their headquarters to Zurich, Switzerland, a politically neutral ground away from the US sanctions on China.

4. Growing Demand for RISC-V in ASIC and FPGA markets

ASIC, which stands for Application Specific Integrated Circuit, are famous for its personalized applications of specific electronic products such as smartphones, laptops, gaming consoles. They are also used in developing hardware that goes behind the specialized applications such as cryptography, artificial intelligence, and medical devices since they need customization and security as its core functionality.

FPGA stands for Field Programmable Gate Arrays that are a class of chips that can be reconfigured on the spot and has application in cutting-edge technologies in the domain of aerospace, defense, telecommunication, and industrial automation as they can adapt to changing environments.

Such markets require flexible and highly scalable ISA such as RISC-V. According to a double-blind study conducted by Siemens Digital Industries in partnership with Wilson in 2020, 23 per cent of projects in ASIC and FPGA markets have incorporated at least one RISC-V processor.

RISC-V Activity by Region

Projects Incorporating RISC-V by Market Segment

While India has enough design talent, the institutional architecture needs a new spirit and support of policymakers.

Adoption Case Study

While India has enough design talent, the institutional architecture needs a new spirit and support by policymakers.

Digital India RISC-V Microprocessor Program, India

On 27th April, 2022, Rajeev Chandrashekhar, MoS MEITY launched 'Digital India RISC-V Microprocessor (DIR-V) Program.' The program aims to develop India's indigenous microprocessors by leveraging RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture.

The program also announced the roadmap for developing an integrated RISC-V ecosystem in India. This includes the announcement of the blueprint of the SHAKTI chip developed by IIT Madras and VEGA Processor developed by C-DAC. For taking the program ahead, Professor V. Kamakoti, Director of IIT Madras is appointed as Chief Architect of the program and Shri. S. Krishnakumar Rao is appointed as Program Manager.

The close collaboration of policymakers and academia for developing new designs is made possible because of the accessibility of RISC-V. While India has enough design talent, the institutional architecture needs a new spirit and support of policymakers. The presence of Rajeev Chandrashekhar, who served as the design team of Intel's x86 microprocessors, is often termed as the father of Intel's Pentium chip domain expertise of the policymaker and plays a critical role in the development of RISC-V ecosystem.

Some of the key applications of SHAKTI and VEGA are as under:

1. SpectroProcessor device used for measuring concentration of biomolecules in spectroscopy is based on the SHAKTI C-class processor
2. QuinProc device that can count the number of red blood cells, white blood cells, and platelets in blood through a microfluidic chip and a camera is based on SHAKTI E-class processor
3. Remote sewage monitoring through 6E Resources for measuring quality of sewage water using sensors which is based on VEGA 32-bit processor

Strong institutional support followed by political willingness of Government of India to create a healthy and self-sustaining chip designing ecosystem has made RISC-V favorable. SHAKTI chip program by IIT Madras has also received support from global semiconductor EDA providers and equipment manufacturers. Synopsys, Applied Materials, Xilinx et.al. considered as the titan of industries in developing core equipment that goes behind the designing of chip.

RISC-V Applications in China's Tech Industry

- 1. Huawei:** Chinese telecom giant Huawei is developing RISC-V based chip known as Kunpeng 920 designed for cloud computing, and big data applications. The chip consists of 64 cores that can run up to 2.6 GHz. The company claims that the chip has 30% higher performance and consumes 30% less power.
- 2. Alibaba:** T-Head, the chip division of Alibaba has launched XianTie910 high-performance processor based on RISC-V architecture. The HPC is favorable for AI and 5G applications and has 16 cores with a clock speed of 2.5 GHz. Hanguang 800, another IoT device processor developed by Alibaba also functions of RISC-V which is used for image recognition and natural language processing.
- 3. Tencent:** Tencent is currently developing RISC-V based chip known as Phoenix designed for cloud gaming and AI applications. The chip has 32 cores and has a clock speed of 2.4 GHz. Tencent also develops RISC-V based chips for its IoT devices such as T-Face that uses facial recognition technology to secure for its smart-home product portfolio.
- 4. Nuclei System Technology:** The Shanghai based RISC-V chipmaker Nuclei System Technology is one of the largest Chinese companies developing RISC-V architecture. Nuclei develops designs that can be customized for real-world needs. The products developed by Nuclei are already used in the Alipay and UnionPay, China's famous payment systems.

Ventana Systems Case Study

InCore Semi, a SoC manufacturer that develops domain-specific hardware accelerators has based its business model on RISC-V architecture ecosystem. As the company mission claims “to harness the power and flexibility of RISC-V architecture,” the company has provided hardware solutions to organizations such as Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) in the form of SoC platform and RISC-V processor cores for their satellites, launch vehicles, and ground stations.

The company has also collaborated with IIT Madras, the research organization that has been developing SHAKTI Processor Project, an indigenous processor ecosystem developed in India. Another key consumer is Tata Consultancy Services that uses InCore designed RISC-V based Smart Metering Solution in the power sector for remote monitoring and control of electricity consumption and billing.

During a panel discussion on the topic of “Emerging Designs” at Semicon India 2023, Neel Gala, CEO of InCore Semiconductors generated a lot of interests on RISC-V amongst the panel members. He raised the question of whether a sudden shift into alternate ISA is a good thing for the semiconductor design markets since ARM is the industry standard and products are developed based on their standardized design architecture.

“...to give you specific examples: smart cards, e-passports, you are looking at energy meters...where India has a protected market...This is where the government can induce policies that have the ability to go Aatmanirbhar without creating chaos in an existing system. There’s enough cake on the table and we are talking volumes...” In this context he also raises the fact that in recent government tenders, for replacing 25 crore meters over the next half decade, even 10 of those chips are Indian IP, that will be a huge volume to work on. And that is the very sector InCore Semi intends to focus on.

InCore Semi Case Study

Contemplating the duopoly of ARM and Intel, Ventana Systems is a chip designing company started by Balaji Baktha and Greg Favor who have spent their career in developing chip designs based on ARM architecture. Speaking at Semicon India 2023, Mr. Baktha who holds the position of CEO at Ventana Systems presented Veyron V1, world's first data center class RISC-V Processor that functions as System of Chips (SoC) for high performance data centre computing. Veyron V1 runs at 3.6 GHz equivalent to HPC chip cores developed by ARM and x86. The 5 nm 3.6 GHz processors are developed by Ventana R&D team in Bengaluru spearheading the RISC-V ecosystem in India.

As the Moore's law is diminishing, the core architecture of the chips needs manipulation that proprietary-based architecture currently lacks. For high performance computing, chip designing demands innovation within the blueprint of the chip design itself, a need that RISC-V based architecture provides. Leveraging that flexibility, Ventana Systems develops scalable chiplets and SoCs that provides a good product differentiation in contrast to traditional semiconductor chips.

For India, data sovereignty is a factor that keeps policymakers interested in the chip designing ecosystems. Given the political neutrality that RISC-V provides, followed by flexibility in the core designs, new chips can be designed that are more secure and less prone to design vulnerabilities that cyber-attackers leverage.

While Ventana System case showcases how flexibility can meet scalability, its application in HPC for data servers is a good way of understanding how RISC-V can be a good differentiator from legacy chip ISA as new chip designers are looking forward to create more products based on RISC-V.

Chip design indigenization and willingness to create a scalable product requires an alternate approach that Indian companies like InCore Semi can work upon by leveraging RISC-V for low-risk computing solutions. While InCore Semi is already involved with the nucleus of industrial SoC consumers, developing a chip design market for low-risk market such as wearables, smart meters, smart cards etc. can come a long way given the volume base that such markets hold.

Governance of RISC-V Ecosystem and Industry Participation

RISC-V International Association is the principal governing body of the RISC-V ecosystem.

RISC-V International Association

RISC-V International Association is the principal governing body of the RISC-V ecosystem. The foundation currently holds 3,950 members spread across 70 countries who include industry leaders, domain experts, and special interest groups. The company website categorically mentions that the foundation keeps a politically neutral position. The foundation currently operates from Zurich, Switzerland as RISC-V International Association.

The association is governed by a board of directors and members of the technical steering committee. The board of directors include the CXOs and senior directors of key fabless and foundry-based chip manufacturers as well as members of research laboratories and academia. As per the Article 14 of 'Articles of RISC-V International Association' board of directors hold the responsibility of providing strategic guidance and overall management of RISC-V International. They are also responsible for overseeing the financial and legal affairs of the association which includes approving the annual budget, ensuring compliance to the Swiss law, and of the Articles of RISC-V International Association.

The technical steering committee includes CTOs, design engineers, and technical design experts holding prestigious positions in semiconductor organizations. The technical steering committee will lead and govern the RISC-V Technical Groupings. The steering committee holds the right to approve the formation, dissolution, and preliminary charter of the technical groups which also includes appointment and removal of the chairs and co-chairs of these groups.

While the technical groupings are responsible for developing specification-based ISA, the technical steering committee decides if it wants to ratify the specific ISAs that meet the quality and compatibility standards of the RISC-V International Association. They also vote on technical matters that influence the RISC-V ISA and related ecosystems. The committee is accountable to the Board of Directors and are obliged to provide a monthly report to the board.

While there are plethora of technical groups that are overseen by the committee, the board of directors and technical steering committee manages, supervises, and monitors the RISC-V architecture. The membership to the organization is inclusive and open to chip making communities who intend to leverage the open-source architecture for developing chip designs that do not use the legacy proprietary chip architecture.

RISC-V Software Ecosystem (RISE)

Termed as the software ecosystem arm of RISC-V, RISE an acronym for 'RISC-V Software Ecosystem' is a grouping of vendors who develop chips for a range of industry sectors - smartphones, automotives, high processing computing, datacenters. The grouping is hosted by Linux Foundation Europe. The members of these groupings are global chip-making giants and original equipment manufacturers. The founding members include MediaTek, Nvidia, Qualcomm Technologies, Red Hat, Samsung, and to everyone's surprise, Intel, the owner of Legacy x86 ISA.

The grouping also supports technical activities related to RISC-V International Association such as creating and ratifying ISA and non-ISA specifications.

These members contribute financially to the grouping as well as provide necessary manpower to develop a “robust software ecosystem” for developing RISC-V compatible devices. The key focus areas of the grouping are in developing an array of software applications that are necessary for developing high-performance computing RISC-V chips so as to increase the scalability and applicability of RISC-V chip architecture for heavy computing applications such as AI data centers, cloud services that leverage quantum computing or industry grade 5G applications.

RISE Members

	Name	Established	Headquarters
	Google	1998	Mountain View, California, USA
	Andes	2005	Hsinchu, Taiwan
	Intel	1968	Santa Clara, California, USA
	Imagination Technologies	1985	Kings Langley, England, UK
	MediaTek	1997	Hsinchu, Taiwan
	Nvidia	1993	Santa Clara, California, USA
	Qualcomm Technologies	1985	San Diego, California, USA
	Red Hat	1993	Raleigh, North Carolina, USA
	Rivos	2021	San Jose, California, USA
	Samsung	1969	Seoul, South Korea
	SiFive	2015	San Mateo, California, USA
	T-Head	2018	Hangzhou, China
	Ventana	2018	Cupertino, California, USA

For India, data sovereignty is a factor that keeps policymakers interested in the chip designing ecosystems.

Acceptance Amongst Industry Giants

The ability to customize the source code for domain specific application is also one of the factors that Qualcomm considers while developing its AI enabled chips used in smartphones.

Qualcomm Technologies

Qualcomm Technologies, a member of RISE in a blogpost mentioned how the telecom chipmaking giant is ‘unlocking the potential of RISC-V.’ Termed as original equipment manufacturer, Qualcomm intends to leverage RISC-V for developing chips that have AI-ML applications, a costly affair for performing at proprietary ISA developers as RISC-V ‘fits that bill’ that legacy architecture won’t, given the heavy licensing fees. Also, the ability to customize the source code for domain specific application is also one of the factors that Qualcomm considers while developing its AI-enabled chips used in smartphones.

Nvidia

Prior to one of the glorious deals struck between ARM and Nvidia, when the GPU giant was close to acquiring ARM, a lot of interest started getting generated to leverage RISC-V in Nvidia products.

However, the deal went south as the United Kingdom government intervened over national security concerns surrounding the geopolitical issues amongst the UK, the USA, and the PRC over the transfer of critical technologies to Chinese market and their likely military use. The Federal Trade Commission of the United States also intervened in 2021 by suing the Nvidia Corp, halting the \$40 billion merger for good.

Intel

Other than being one of the founding members of RISE, Intel has developed its next gen retail market processors such as Nios V Processor, and commercial FPGA processors for HPC businesses on RISC V ISA. Intel's participation is intriguing, given the nature of its business model.

While the chip industry is turning competitive in the domain of chip designing because of lesser barriers to entry, the chip foundry market is relatively oligopolistic for legacy chips and borderline monopolistic by Taiwan based Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Corporation (TSMC) when it comes to manufacturing cutting-edge 2 nm-5 nm chips.

One of the reasons why Intel spearheads this grouping is to boost its foundry arm, Intel Foundry. Intel is one of the few legacy chipmakers who spearheaded the microprocessors and personal computer revolution back in 1980s and since then continues to manufacture its own chips.

In one of the white papers published by Intel, Intel has developed a detailed RISC-V strategy for its FPGA market. FPGA are programmable segments of semiconductor chips that are relatively malleable in their architecture for specific domain applications. The white paper acknowledges the “widespread commercial adoption” of RISC-V “across industries.” The adoption is in “embedded automotives to hyperscale artificial intelligence, from 5G to high-performance computing (HPC) and beyond.”

The vendor diversification for sustaining geopolitical turbulence increases the likelihood of industry giants such as Nvidia, Intel, and Qualcomm to increase their financial bets in developing RISC-V ecosystem. While none of the industry players publicly acknowledges the stress of geopolitics on their business models, alternatives such as RISC-V are within the radars of these chipmakers, which generates the confidence of new chip designing entrants on RISC-V architecture.

In a public announcement, Nvidia declared the termination of the deal on February 7th, 2022. The press release mentions “the parties agreed to terminate the agreement because of significant regulatory challenges preventing the consummation of the transaction, despite good faith efforts by the parties.” Following this, the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), the competition and anti-trust watchdog of the UK government on the very next day announced the abandonment of the deal.

The key reasons and implications of the deal’s cancellation quoted ‘competition grounds’ since Nvidia’s unrestricted access to ARM’s intellectual property warrants monopolization across different verticals of datacenter CPU value chain as well as in Internet-of-Things, automotive, and gaming consoles market.

While analysts claimed that such merger might complicate the underlying political neutrality of ARM, often considered as the Switzerland of chip makers, the causal chain brings Nvidia’s extension to Chinese market which stands at \$1.2 billion in the data centre segment in China and Hong Kong for the fiscal year 2022. Not to mention Nvidia’s A800 AI processor that was designed specifically for the Chinese markets. The delivery of these chips is due in 2023 and 2024.

Following this debacle, Nvidia ventured into tapping the potential of RISC-V for developing its high-performance computing processors to diversify its dependence on ARM ISA. Other than being a founder member of RISE, a RISC-V processor code-named NV-RISCV was developed by Nvidia that functioned as a GPU controller core that communicated with the massive pool of GPU cores inside a system. Nvidia has acknowledged the potential of RISC-V as an alternate to ARM architecture during the 4th RISC-V workshop in 2016 comparing the performance of ARM segments with RISC-V Rocket. Membership in RISE gives Nvidia access to RISC-V ISA while it continues with ARM as its primary ISA provider.

The growing polarization between China and the United States paints a gloomy picture as it jeopardizes the neutrality of RISC-V.

Other Open-Source ISA

Recently, US President Joe Biden was pressurized by a bipartisan group of lawmakers to take a hardline approach in the matter of China accessing RISC-V ISA after the ban of ARM and Intel's x86 access to Chinese chipmakers.

As RISC ecosystem has gained enough traction and public eye, the association is under fire for its application in the Chinese chip market. Recently, US President Joe Biden was pressurized by a bipartisan group of lawmakers to take a hardline approach in the matter of China accessing RISC-V ISA after the ban of ARM and Intel's x86 access to Chinese chipmakers. As a result, there is a wider industry skepticism on how much can RISC V International Association can hold the line since majority of financiers and members of committee hail from the western chipmaking giants.

Given the issue at hand, there already exist certain alternatives to other open-source ISA provider other than RISC-V that are growing their foothold within a niche ecosystem of products. If enough traction and political support is provided to any of these open-source ISA, they can be the next big thing after RISC-V in open-source market.

POWER

POWER Instruction Set Architecture is developed by Integrated Business Machines (IBM) mainly used in servers, embedded systems, and supercomputers. OpenPOWER Foundation, a collaborative forum of researchers, companies, and developers leverage POWER ISA to develop open hardware and software projects. While the ISA has lesser penetration in open-source development space, it does have comprehensive applications in selected spaces.

ARC

ARC ISA is developed by Synopsys, an industry leader in EDA software tools. While Synopsys sells proprietary ARC processor cores under commercial license, it has also developed an open-source alternative through embARC Open-Source Platform.

Tensilica

Developed by Cadence Design Systems, a semiconductor chip manufacturing equipment maker has developed Tensilica ISA that is used in creating custom instruction sets for audio, video, imaging, and wireless communication tools. Just like Synopsys, Cadence also sells the Tensilica ISA under a commercial license while also maintaining an open-source version of the ISA for some of its cores under Open Tensilica Initiative.

As RISC ecosystem has gained enough traction and public eye, the association is under fire for its application in the Chinese chip market.

Conclusion

For years, the global semiconductor industry has embraced globalization like never before.

A lot of interest is getting generated in the RISC-V especially in the design ecosystem. For years, the global semiconductor industry has embraced globalization like never before. The industry originated as a product of globalized supply chain where entity that is the most efficient in developing innovative products and commercializing them into final retail product has survived waves of industry cycle. The industry requires heavy and patient capital investment which has also developed the venture capital market in China and other emerging economies where government participation has increased like never before.

However, the barriers to entry have also parallelly increased regardless of increased industry participation in chip designing market because of the heavy capital investment that goes behind securing an ISA provider.

RISC-V holds a critical edge over competing ISA providers because of its proactive governance and participation of existing industry giants in the governing structure of RISC-V International Association. Their contribution in decision-making nuclei or financial overlay in developing the RISC-V ecosystem matters a lot in deciding how successful RISC-V will be.

The organization has clarified its intentions to stay politically neutral as political interest groups are rallying popular support given the increasing “tech-nationalism” visible in both US and China in last five years. The business interest demand access to market while government demands regulations. These interests have been contradicting for decades now.

Currently, the chip giants are considering RISC-V a reliable alternate for licensed ISA categorically for its technical prowess and, hence, continue their unwavering support the growth of RISC-V ecosystem as articulated in the report. However, the question stays that how long can RISC-V International Association hold its ground of neutrality if economies like China continue to leverage RISC-V to develop its own semiconductor ecosystem just like the United States did in the Cold War era?

The growing polarization between China and the United States paints a gloomy picture as it jeopardizes the neutrality of RISC-V. In International Relations, the only way to assure neutrality is to ensure strategic autonomy. However, participation of national actors in the governance of RISC-V continues to entangle with the codes of Swiss neutrality. While no one can deny the sustainability of RISC-V ecosystem in technical domains, the growing zero-sum tech nationalism in China and the United States raises alarm for the global semiconductor industry.

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